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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ARTICLES

Biernacki, A. B. / Sharankov, N.: A Hitherto Unknown Aspect of the Military Activity of the <i>Legio I Italica</i> in the Light of a Recently Discovered Pedestal with a Greek Inscription from <i>Novae</i>	1
Grozdanova, G.: Relative Chronology of the Pottery of the Early Medieval Lower Danube Popina-Garvan Archaeological Group	21
Komar, O.: Archaeological and Archaeomagnetic Dating of Early Medieval Kantsyrka Type Pottery	39
Khamaiko, N.: The Late Medieval Sites of the Yatseva Balka Type in the Dnieper Rapids Region: Problems of Dating and Interpretation	71
Komatarova-Balinova, E. / Penkova, P.: The “Horse Amulets” from the Collections of Vidin and Vratsa Museums – a Modest Contribution to a Continuous Discussion	93

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On the cover: a brass amulet-horse ridden by a male head, NW Bulgaria; see the paper of Komatarova-Balinova / Penkova in this issue; photo by Krasimir Georgiev.

Archaeological and Archaeomagnetic Dating of Early Medieval Kantsyrka Type Pottery

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Abstract: The Early Medieval Alan pottery production center in Kantsyrka valley on Dnieper river was the first evidence of the resumption of mass craft production of goods in the steppe of the Northern Black Sea region during the post-Roman period. This fact, as well as the fact of the unquestionable Alanian North Caucasian origin of the pottery tradition, constantly attract the attention of researchers to the problems of ethnic origin of the population, the reasons for its migration to the Dniepr region, and the lifetime of the settlements.

The question of chronology remains one of the most acute problems. Pottery of the Kantsyrka type was dated to the second half of the 7th – 8th centuries AD soon after its discovery and attribution as an independent cultural type based on analogies and finds of ceramics of this type together with coins in complexes of nomads. After 1973, three archaeomagnetic dates were added to the base of the dating, obtained for pottery kilns from the three workshops of the Lyubymivka settlement in Kantsyrka valley. The initial archaeomagnetic framework proposed for the time of existence of the workshop, “6th – 7th centuries AD”, differed from archaeological dating. This led to the emergence of two trends in the dating and interpretation of the pottery center in the Kantsyrka valley. The first interpretation explained the appearance of Alan pottery centers at the Dnieper region area as the first wave of the resettlement of the North Caucasus population within the Khazar Khaganate (after AD 665), prior to the formation of the Saltiv culture at the Don region in the middle of the 8th century. The second interpretation relied on the archaeo-magnetic dates and assumed the emergence of the center in the framework of the Proto-Bulgarian tribal union in the 6th – 7th centuries AD, with the subsequent transfer of pottery making traditions in the Danube region after AD 681.

Modern analysis of the occurrence of the Kantsyrka type ceramics in the archaeological complexes of nomads and Slavs in the Dnieper region still does not explain the dating of the appearance of the Kantsyrka pottery center to the 6th century. The *terminus post quem* is determined by Byzantine coins from Kelegei complex, minted in AD 644/645. The upper limit is determined by the similarity of the manufacturing technique of big jugs from Taraniv ravine (Machukhy), the similarity of the small group of jugs from Fedorivka settlement to the three-handled jugs of the Saltiv culture and also by the production of derivatives of the Kantsyrka type jugs at the Mayaki settlement in Don region. An archaeological date of the Kantsyrka type pottery can be set within the framework of AD 645-740.

The hypothesis of the transfer of the Kantsyrka pottery traditions to the Danube region by Bulgarian tribes of Asparukh after AD 681 cannot currently be illustrated by real finds of fragments of Kantsyrka type pottery in Bulgaria. Vessels resembling some Kantsyrka elements of the decoration and design of jugs were found in graves of three Bulgarian cemeteries: Bdintsi, Balchik and Kyulevcha, dated from the late 7th till the middle of the 8th century. They correspond to chronological frames of nomad complexes from the Dnieper region with finds of original Kantsyrka type pottery.

Archaeomagnetic dates of Kantsyrka kilns do not contradict the archaeological dating. Yet in 1982 updated archaeomagnetic dating of kilns from Kantsyrka were published: two kilns (# 13 and # 17) were dated to the 7th century, and one (# 12) – to the 8th century AD. Modern verification of the chronological interpretation of old archaeomagnetic data using the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* and ARCH3K.1, SHA.DIF.14K, CALS3K.3 models produced a fully acceptable result in good agreement with archaeological dates: kiln 13 – AD 634-723; kiln 17 – AD 691-770; kiln 12 – AD 704-769. This result can be improved with a further development of archaeomagnetic analysis tools and databases.

Key words: pottery, Early Medieval, Eastern Europe, archaeomagnetic dating.

HISTORY AND CURRENT STATE OF THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEM

The Early Medieval pottery production center in the Kantsyrka valley (near Fedorivka village, Zaporizhia region and Lubymivka village, Dnipropetrovsk region, Ukraine) was discovered in 1929 by Volodymyr Grinchenko. The initial excavations near Fedorivka village took place between 1929-1931, during which the remains of 2 settlements with 5 workshops and 10 kilns were studied. A huge amount of pottery sherds with attractive decoration (**fig. 1/1-3, fig. 2/1-4, 3**) confirmed that vessels were produced for sale, not for the needs of nearby settlements inhabitants. In 1954, Oleksandr Bodians'kyi discovered another kiln in the third settlement in Kantsyrka valley and thus discovered that these sites were not destroyed by the reservoir of the Dnipro hydroelectric power station ("DniproHES"). Alla Smilenko (Braichevska) continued the excavations of the Lubymivka settlement (1955, 1964-1970) and studied 7 workshops and 8 kilns with similar pottery (**fig. 1/4-6**) (Брайчевська 1961; Сміленко 1975, 118-157).

Volodymyr Grinchenko had no possibility to publish results of his work because of political repressions in Stalin's USSR from which he suffered. His only article was published as a brief version after his death (Грінченко 1950). Materials of excavations in Kantsyrka valley were partially used and published later by Alla Smilenko and Tatiana Minaeva (Брайчевська 1961; Мінаєва 1961; Сміленко 1975). In field diaries and manuscripts of short reports Volodymyr Grinchenko attributed the discovered pottery with polishing and relief decoration (**fig. 1, 3**) to the "North Caucasian culture" or "the Verkhni Saltiv culture" and dated it to the 7th – 9th centuries AD. A short report of the "DniproHES building expedition" for the year 1930, signed by the head of the expedition Dmytro Yavornytsky, named the Kantsyrka center "Alan" and dated it to the 7th – 9th centuries AD. (Яворницький 2010, 44). A final collective report for the years 1927-1931 attributed the Kantsyrka center as "the North Caucasian culture of the 7th – 9th centuries AD". This culture was considered to be a broader phenomenon, including the Verkhni Saltiv and Mayaki settlements, a pottery making center in Machuhy (Taraniv ravine) and rich complexes ("hoards") from Voznesenka, Mala Pereshchepyna, Kelegei¹ (Дніпрельстанівська археологічна експедиція 1931, 11-13).

Connection of the Kantsyrka center with complexes of the Pereshchepyna type was revealed by Volodymyr Grinchenko in 1930 during excavations of the Voznesenka complex. Numerous sherds of Kantsyrka type pottery were found in cultural layers within the stone structure (**fig. 4**). In 1932, Grinchenko also studied the collection of the Kelegei complex at the Kherson museum. He noted in a diary that fragments of pottery from Kelegei were similar to the Kantsyrka type and made few rubbing drawings of such potsherds (**fig. 5/1, 2**). He explained the appearance of Kantsyrka settlements with pottery production workshops on the Lower Dnieper by the needs of an administrative center that built Voznesenka "hillfort", and the same explanation was proposed for the similar Machukhy (Taraniv ravine) kiln (**fig. 8/1-3**) located near the richest Mala Pereshchepyna find and complexes from Zachepylivka and Makukhivka. The dating of these pottery production centers Volodymyr Grinchenko based on Byzantine coins from complexes of the Pereshchepyna type (the latest of which were minted in the reign of Emperor Constans II, AD 641-668), taking the

¹ Toponyms of archaeological sites from the territory of Ukraine are often transmitted in publications in European languages in transcriptions from Russian-language publications, which creates confusion due to the multiplicity of the name forms and transliterations. As a result, such sites are difficult to localize on modern maps.

Fig. 1. Jugs of the Kantsyrka type: 1-3 Fedorivka (after photos from Volodymyr Grinchenko's personal archive – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11, # Г/7); 4-6 Lyubymivka (4 after Брайчевська 1961; 6 after Сміленко 1965). 1-3 – scale is different

year 668 as *terminus post quem* and the 8th century as a basic time of settlement's existence (Грінченко 1937).

In the manuscript about the Kelegei complex, Oleksandr Tahtai also called the discovered pottery “the North Caucasian type of the 7th – 9th centuries AD” and compared it with finds from Verkhni Saltiv, Kantsyrka and Machukhy (Taraniv ravine) (Тахтаї 1932). He believed that Alan pottery workshops on Lower Dnieper worked for the highest social stratum of the steppe population, and even distinguished a special “Alanian stage” in the history of the steppe region, following the “Sarmatian-Gothic stage”.

Alla Smilenko considered analogies from the excavations of the Verkhni Saltiv settlement noting that Saltiv jugs differ in the technique of decoration and the shape of the neck from Kantsyrka three-handled vessels. In her opinion, finds of Kantsyrka pottery in the Voznesenka complex mean a diffusion of this type of ceramics in the Lower Dnieper region started from the early 8th century (Брайчевська 1961, 117-118). Tatiana Minaeva applied a different approach for dating of the Kantsyrka type ware based on a comparison of manufacturing

techniques and the shape of vessels using pottery from monuments of the North Caucasus Alan culture. A combination of the Kantsyrka type ware features corresponded to the third period of the development of the Alan pottery of the Kuban' region (end of 7th – 9th centuries AD) and exact analogies from the Galiat tomb dated by Arabic dirham minted in the 1st half of the 8th century. Tatiana Minaeva considered settlements of the Kantsyrka type to be related to the Saltiv culture, but only as a result of a similarity of both cultures with the culture of the Alan of the North Caucasus (Мінаєва 1961). More categorical attribution was offered by Svetlana Pletnyova, who considered Kantsyrka settlements and the Voznesenka complex to be the most western sites of the Saltiv culture (Плетнёва 1967, 7, 101, 102).

The next stage in of study of the problem was inspired by the archaeomagnetic dating of three kilns from the 1965-1970 excavations at Kantsyrka valley. As Alla Smilenko reported, archaeomagnetic dating was conducted by Oleg Rusakov and Grygoriy Zagniy. Kiln # 13 was dated to the second half of the 6th century; kilns # 12 and # 17 were dated to the end of the 6th – beginning of the 7th century AD. New archaeomagnetic dating forced Alla Smilenko to change frames of archaeological dating of the Kantsyrka settlement and Voznesenka complex as well, and assumed their existence from the turn of the 6th and 7th centuries until the end of the 7th century (Сміленко 1975, 155). The new dating also changed the historical context of the Kantsyrka pottery production center and caused a division of the discussion into two main lines.

The first one did not take the archaeomagnetic dating into account and relied on archaeological dating methods as before.

Oleg Pryhodnyuk attributed the upper boundary of the dating of Kantsyrka settlements to the 8th century relying on the dating of the Voznesenka complex. He also noticed the presence of fragments of Kantsyrka ceramics on Slavic settlements of Stetsivka and Pen'kivka, but not in complexes of the Molocharnia stage. He used this to date the appearance of Kantsyrka workshops to the second half of the 7th century (Приходнюк 1980, 91). Later, he dated the Kantsyrka settlements without any explanation to the 6th – 7th centuries (Приходнюк 2001, 41), but also noted contacts of the Pastyr's'ke hillfort with the Kantsyrka pottery center and dated the hillfort to the second half of the 7th – first half of the 8th century (Приходнюк 2005, 65). On the basis of analysis of the distribution of fragments of Kantsyrka pottery at forest-steppe Slavic settlements Yaroslav Volodarets-Urbanovych and Andrii Skyba also supposed the parallel coexistence of the Pastyr's'ke hillfort and the Kantsyrka center and dated the last one to the second half of the 7th – first half of the 8th century (Володарець-Урбанович / Скиба 2011).

Valerii Flyorov pointed to discovery of the third pottery center that manufactured big three-handled pitchers of the Kantsyrka type on the Mayaki settlement and confirmed the opinion of Svetlana Pletnyova about Kantsyrka and Machukhy as the most western sites of the Saltiv culture (Флєров 1981, 178). Anatolii Ambroz dated the Voznesenka complex to the beginning of the 8th century and referred to the opinion of Gennadii Afanasyev, that pottery similar to the Kantsyrka type pitchers appear at the North Caucasus region only in the 8th century (Амброз 1981, 18). Following Tatiana Minaeva and

Svetlana Pletnyova, Evgenii Goryunov supposed that both pottery centers belonged to the Saltiv culture and appeared no earlier than the late 7th century (Горюнов 1987, 3-6).

Aleksandr Aibabin considered a vessel from the Yasynove complex (**fig. 4/3**) to be produced in the Kantsyrka workshop. He dated the complex to the first half of the 8th century and supposed that the settlements of the Alan potters from Kantsyrka valley and Taraniv ravine appeared in the Dnieper region at the end of the 7th century, along with the nomadic Pereshchepyna culture of the early Khazar Khaganate (Айбабин 1985, 196, 201-202). This view was repeated in later works (Айбабин 1999; 2013; Aibabin 2005). The concept of the Pereshchepyna culture was developed further in my works on a wider range of nomadic complexes (Комар 1999; 2000; 2006; 2013). The appearance of Alan craft centers at the Dnieper region area was considered to be the first stage of the resettlement of North Caucasus population within the Khazar Khaganate (shortly after AD 665), preceding the mass migration at the Don region in the middle of the 8th century that caused the formation of the Saltiv culture. Florin Curta explained the emergence of the Kantsyrka center by the economic activity of the Khazar Khaganate and dated the workshops to the second half of the 7th century – early 8th century (Curta 2008, 168).

Michel Kazanski initially stated that Alan sites of Kantsyrka and Machukhy had appeared during the second half of the 7th century and predated the Saltiv culture, which emerged in the middle of the 8th century (Kazanski 1987, 87). But later the researcher began to lean toward the use of the “early” archaeomagnetic dating in order to agree the dating of Kantsyrka type pottery with the proposed new dating of Pereshchepyna type complexes to the first half of the 7th century (Kazanski 2013, 808; Казанский 2014, 65).

The second line used the “early” dating (6th – 7th centuries AD) mainly to draw other historical pictures or to give alternative ethnic interpretation for settlements of the Kantsyrka type and complexes of the Pereshchepyna type. Vasil Gyuzelev considered the pottery production center in Kantsyrka valley to have been left by the group of Protobulgarians (Гюзелев 1979, 15). Stanislav Stanilov dated the center to the 6th – 7th centuries but stated that the evidence of the arrangement of the pottery production of gray ware in Bulgaria by Kantsyrka potters were still absent (Станилов 1984, 101-103). Dimitar Dimitrov believed that the Kantsyrka workshops were created by the Protobulgarians, who borrowed pottery traditions from Caucasian Alans, but he didn't insist that the Kantsyrka pottery tradition had been transferred to Bulgaria (Димитров 1987, 113-121). This idea was discussed and developed by Georgi Atanasov (Атанасов 2015, 89-91, 101-116, 209-222).

Oleg Bubenok previously dated the Kantsyrka settlements to the 6th – 7th centuries but considered them as the earliest sites of the Saltiv type (Бубенок 1997, 25). Later, he decided that the appearance of workshops was connected with the khan Kuvrat activity, and the end of settlements was connected with the invasion of Khazars. So, the date of the center must have been in the narrow mid- to late-7th century framework (Бубенок 2005, 8-9).

In 1982 Grygoriy Zagniy and Oleg Rusakov published updated archaeomagnetic dating of kilns from Kantsyrka: two kilns

(# 13 and # 17) were dated to the 7th century, and one (# 12) – to the 8th century (Загний / Русаков 1982, 124, 125). Updated archaeomagnetic data was used by Csanad Balint (Balint 1989, 120) and Alla Smilenko (Smilenko 1990, 323; Приходнюк et al. 1990, 331). But, for unknown reasons it has not been in demand by other researchers for several decades. In a number of researches, only initial archaeomagnetic dates of Kantsyrka kilns continued to be quoted without any references to published works of geophysicists (Гавритухин / Обломский 1996, 123; Рашев 2004, 142; Хрисимов 2009, 29; Kazanski 2013, 808; Казанский 2014, 65; Атанасов 2015, 89; 2017, 23; Дончева-Петкова et al. 2016, 91).

Attempts to expand the dating base for pottery of the Kantsyrka type were minimal. Igor Gavritukhin and Andrei Oblomskii referred to the opinion of Vladimir Malashev, that technological features of Kantsyrka type pottery in the Alan culture of Kislovodsk valley correspond to the chronological stages with belt ornaments in “heraldic” style from the second half of the 6th till the early 8th century (Гавритухин / Обломский 1996, 123, 142, 145; Обломский 2012, 20, 21). Yaroslav Volodarets-Urbanovych tried to expand the number of chronological indicators by use of the objects from the cultural layers of Slavic settlements, where individual fragments of Kantsyrka ceramics were found. In his opinion, Slavic settlements with such finds can be dated in frames from the second quarter of the 7th until the first half of the 8th century (Володарец-Урбанович 2012; Володарец-Урбанович 2014a, 12). Both approaches involve methodological weaknesses. The first one refers not to exact analogies in shape and technique but to the set of separated “common features”. The second operates with random finds from multilayered settlements, rather than closed archaeological complexes.

We clearly see that the main problem is reconciling of archaeological and archaeomagnetic dating underlined by many authors (Гавритухин / Обломский 1996, 123; Рашев 2004, 142; Kazanski 2013, 808; Казанский 2014, 65; Володарец-Урбанович 2014b, 53; Атанасов 2015, 89; Дончева-Петкова et al. 2016, 91). So, the main task now is to find out whether a discrepancy really exists or the problem lies in the misuse of archaeomagnetic data.

ARCHAEOLOGICAL DATING OF KANTSYRKA TYPE POTTERY

Excavations of workshops and pottery furnaces in the Kantsyrka valley did not provide reliable datable artifacts. No coins, ornaments, or imports were found, only small fragments of amphorae whose shape of ware could not be reconstructed. These facts contradict the argument for the big trading center and rather attest the dependent position of craftsmen. However, it should be specified that only the production area was currently studied, not living areas or the cemeteries. In such conditions, the usual procedure of the archaeological dating is possible only for production of the Kantsyrka workshops found in archeological complexes of neighbors.

Based on the waste of production in kilns and around, the most numerous product of Kantsyrka valley potters were large three-handed jugs for water storage (**fig. 1/1**). Less frequent were the medium-sized and smaller jugs with one handle (**fig. 1/2, 3, 5, 6**). The kitchen pots and *pithos*-like pots for storage were relatively rare (**fig. 3/1, 2, 5**), and the rarest were vessels of small sizes: mugs, jars (**fig. 2/1-6**). Vessels

Fig. 2. Mugs and small vessels of the Kantsyrka type: 1-5 Fedorivka (2-5 after photos from Volodymyr Grinchenko's personal archive – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11, # Г/7); 6 Lyubymivka; 7 Yasynove (after Айбабин 1985); 8 Shylovka, barrow 2

were covered with “rich” decoration, superfluous in comparison to the ordinary Alan pottery of North Caucasus (compare: Малашев 2001, рис. 49-52). Kantsyrka type polished dark gray ware (**fig. 2/2, 6, fig. 3/3, 4, fig. 8/2, 3**) in small fragments hardly differs from the vessels of the Saltiv culture, Volyntseve culture and even some types of pottery of the Sarmatian and Golden Horde periods; sherds of light gray ware sometimes resemble local cookware of the Chernyakhiv culture. Thus, the cultural attribution of small fragments without traceological and petrographic analyses is not productive. The Kantsyrka type ceramics with relief decoration are more informative – applied knobbls, strips, sometimes thumbed or decorated with comb; deep grooving on neck and center of the body; grooved waves and carved zigzags with toothed tool; wide grooves along the wet surface instead of the polished with narrow tool on a dry surface (**fig. 3/1, 2, 5-13**). Combinations of these elements on gray wheel-made ceramics are most typical for the Kantsyrka type pottery.

Only a small number of finds outside of the Kantsyrka valley fully match the criteria of Kantsyrka type pottery. And even fewer of sites meet requirements for dateable complexes. The next problem is that some complexes were discovered in 1920-1940 and were kept in Ukrainian museums, heavily damaged during the Second World War. Part of the collections and the field documentation is currently lost or de-passportized. Especially, little data is preserved about ceramics. This is the current situation for the important Voznesenka, Kelegei and Zachepylivka complexes.

Fig. 3. Fragments of pottery from the Fedorivka settlement (after photos and drawings from Volodymyr Grinchenko's personal archive – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11, # Г/7)

Voznesenka (now in Zaporizhia city) – a large memorial building with ritual complexes (Грінченко 1950; Мацулевич 1959). Sherds of pottery are still not identifiable in the museum collections that keep part of objects from the *Voznesenka* site. Volodymyr Grinchenko described gray ware potsherds in diaries and in field reports as fragments of big *Kantsyrka* type jugs with polished and relief decoration and also small “jars” (“*kubyshka*”) without a precise description of the shape (maybe like **fig. 2/3, 6**). Few photos of potsherds from the Volodymyr Grinchenko's archive (**fig. 4**) leave no doubt that these were fragments of *Kantsyrka* type big jugs.

The chronological position of the *Voznesenka* complex is the next chronological horizon after *Mala Pereshchepyna* and *Kelegei* (Амброз 1981; Гавригунин / Обломский 1996; Комар 1999; 2006; Aibabin 2006; Айбабин 2013). There were only a few attempts to contest this position. Nikolai Hrisimov dated the *Voznesenka* complex to 620-640, before *Mala Pereshchepyna* (Хрисимов 2009). But, he ignored a whole Eastern European set of later analogies and used only a small part of objects, instead of a full composition of the complex. The second alternative trend marks attempts to reanimate old hypothesis of

Fig. 4. Fragments of jugs from the Voznesenka complex (after photos from Volodymyr Grinchenko's personal archive – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11; # Г/3). Scale is different

Mikhail Miller about the Voznesenka complex as the grave of Prince Svyatoslav Igorevich (died in 972) (Білецький 2012; Білецький / Шаповалов 2014), based on mistakes and wrong descriptions of finds (Комар 2014, 245-251).

Analogies to objects of the “nomad” group from the complex are found together with a coin of Constantine IV (669-674) in Ozora-Totipuszta (Garam 1992, 146; Somogy 1997, 71-72), a coin of Leontius II (695-698) in the Romanovskaya barrow (Семенов 1985, 91-92) and with a bracteate of Justinian II (705-711) in Камунта (Уварова 1902, Taf. V, # 435; Комар 2010, 187, 188).

Aleksandr Aibabin stated that the control stamp on the silver statuette of an eagle with snake from Voznesenka (Мацулевич 1959) is typical for the time of Constans II (641-668) or Constantine IV (668-684) (Aibabin 2006, 59; Айбабин 2013, 293). This information is not fully correct. Control stamps from Voznesenka (rosette and rectangular) had been struck in the same Byzantine center with spoons from the Novobayazet hoard and few other items dated by stamps of Heraclius with sons (613-641), Constans II alone (642-654) or Constantine IV (668-684) (Мацулевич 1959, 187-190; Dodd 1961, ## 94-98; 1964, 246-247; 1993, 221). Erica Cruikshank Dodd places this center somewhere in Asia Minor. The inscription on the rectangular stamp of the eagle from Voznesenka doesn't match to any of these stamps, or to the rectangular stamp from the Zamostye hoard, attributed by Vera Zaleskaya as a stamp of Constantine IV (668-685) (Родинкова 2012). Since this whole series of readable rectangular stamps and the rosette stamps belong to emperors of the 7th century (Heraclius and his descendants), an exact reading of the stamp on the statuette would unlikely change the absolute date of the Voznesenka complex objects, set on the basis of dated analogies in frames of the last third of the 7th – early 8th centuries AD.

Kelegei (now Gladkivka, Kherson region) – a ritual complex with bones of a horse (Фабрициус 1927; Айбабин 1991; Prichodnjuk / Chardaev 2001). Descriptions of the pottery from the complex have been made in manuscripts of Oleksandr Tahtai (Тахтаї 1932). According to the manuscript, fragments of amphora and three vessels of the “North Caucasian type” were gathered in the place of discovery of the complex. Drawings of ceramics, unfortunately, are missing among attached illustrations, and there is only a photo of the inside part of the bottom of vessel (fig. 5/3).

Fig. 5. Fragments of jugs from Kelegei (1-3) and Zachepylivka (4) complexes (1, 2 after rubbing drawings from Volodymyr Grinchenko's diary – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 18, #105; 3 after Тахрай 1932; 4 after Тахрай 1930). Scale is different

Two big jugs of gray clay with high neck and flat handles were covered with darker engobe. One of them was decorated with vertical polished lines. The second was decorated in a more sophisticated technique with applied strips, deep grooving on the neck, grooved waves and grids of polished lines. Apparently, Volodymyr Grinchenko made rubbing drawings of sherds of the second jug (fig. 5/1, 2). The third “pot or jar” of yellow clay with dark gray engobe and a polished “shiny” surface was smaller and had thinner sherds. The decoration was polished with arcuate lines and applied knobbls on shoulders.

The second jug from Kelegei looks precisely like Kantsyrka type pottery. The description of the first one is closer to jugs from the kiln in Machukhy (fig. 7/2, 3). The third small vessel by description is comparable to mugs of North Caucasian Alans (Малашев 2001, рис. 53, 55, 56). This kind of vessel in gray clay was produced at Kantsyrka (fig. 2/1-3), but without decoration as described. Decoration in shape of arcs of lines is also present on the mug from the Shylovka barrow 2 (fig. 4/8).

The latest coin from the necklace of the Kelegei complex was minted in the reign of Constans II (642-646), possibly in AD 644/645 according to the indiction number (Семёнов 1991, 126, рис. 1; Hahn 1981, 124, Taf. 20/5). The “nomadic” part of objects from Kelegei is completely analogous to the complex from Mala Pereshchepyna. This chronological horizon reflects realities of the nomadic culture depicted in the wall paintings of the Afrasib palace (circa AD 662) (see for details: Комар 2006; 2008).

Zachepylivka (Poltava region) – a ritual complex with bones of a horse (Смиленко 1968; Комар / Хардаев 2012). Among the illustra-

tions of the manuscript of Oleksandr Tahtai (Тахтаї 1930), there is a photograph of one fragment of ceramic (**fig. 5/4**). The shape of the neck and relief technique of decoration are identical to Kantsyrka type big water storage jugs (**fig. 1/1, fig. 3/8**) and very close to fragments of a jug from Voznesenka (**fig. 4/3**). A small amount of collected potsherds indicates that the vessel was not part of the complex, but rather belongs to traces of ritual actions at the site.

The “nomadic” part of objects from Zachepylivka is similar to Voznesenka and Yasynove and belongs to the same chronological horizon (Комар / Хардаев 2012). A set of Byzantine coins from the complex is close to Mala Pereshchepyna. The latest coins from Zachepylivka were minted in AD 642-646 (Hahn 1981, 124, Taf. 20/3b), but the formation of the complex falls on a period of a long gap in proceeds of Byzantine coins to nomads of the Northern Black Sea region (AD 647-695).

Yasynove (now Yasenove, Odesa region) – a ritual complex with bones of a horse (Posta 1905, 350-351, Abb. 213; Айбабин 1985). A small vessel from Yasynove (**fig. 2/7**) is frequently called a “jug” but it has no spout. It is more correct to call this type a ceramic mug. The shape of vessel and its proportions are identical to finds from Kantsyrka settlements (**fig. 2/1, 2**).

The vessel from Shylovka barrow 2 (Багаутдинов, Богачёв, Зубов 1998) is similar but slightly differs in shape of body (**fig. 2/8**). The top of vessel was broken and restored. Its sharp edge was polished and a slit for draining water had been made. So, it is impossible now to establish whether the vessel was originally a mug or a small jug. Shylovka barrow is located very far from the Dnieper region – in Middle Volga, so the differences between the mugs are not surprising. It is more likely that the Shylovka mug was made in another workshop using a similar technology and tradition that the Kantsyrka potters used.

Analogies to ornaments and details of horse equipment from Yasynove found in the previously mentioned Voznesenka complex and at the Romanovskaya barrow (with a coin of Leontius II minted in 695-698). Also, similar belt decorations were found in Old Turkic grave of the 8th century at Kazakhstan (Хасенова 2015). The Shylovka barrow 2 is dated no earlier than the Voznesenka complex (Комар 2010, 99-125).

A jug from the grave 1, barrow 8, near Staronizhesteblievskaya (Атавин / Паромов 1991, 153, рис. 2) in the Kuban region differs from jugs of the Kantsyrka type in shape and in the manner of polishing. Despite the fact that the jug was found in the burial of the Voznesenka horizon, it is close to the jugs of the Saltiv tradition.

Budyshche (Cherkasy region) – a settlement of the Pen'kivka culture (Приходнюк 1990). Fragments of a jug (**fig. 6/1**) found in the filling of pit-house # 3. A jug was decorated with applied strips, wide polished lines on the neck, with grid of polished lines on the upper part of body and vertical lines in lower part (**fig. 6/1b**). Vessel from Budyshche fully matches the criteria of Kantsyrka type pottery in shape, but combination of vertical strips and grids of polished lines is also close to the Saltiv jug from the Mayaki cemetery (**fig. 8/5**).

Other finds from pit-house # 3 – fragments of handmade pots, iron buckle and tools (Приходнюк 1990, рис. 7, 10/4, 10, 13, 23). Decoration of handmade pottery with strips on the neck of pots and

Fig. 6. Reconstruction of jugs from Slavic settlements: 1 Budyshche, pit-house 3 (1a after Приходнюк 1990); 2 Pastyr's'ke, pit-house in sector XIV/1949

notches on the rim is common for the final third stage of the Pen'kivka culture (Приходнюк 1998, 40-60). Absence of precise absolute markers in complexes with Pen'kivka ceramics allows researchers to move the upper boundary of the culture in a wide range from the first third of the 7th century to the middle of the 8th century, which does not help in determining the exact date of existence of the Kantsyrka type pottery.

Stetsivka (Cherkasy region) – a settlement of the late Pen'kivka and early Luka-Raiky culture (Петров 1963). Fragments of big gray pitchers with applied knobs and strips, grids of polished lines, wide grooved lines had been attributed as Kantsyrka type pottery by Viktor Petrov (Петров 1963, 228-229, рис. 11). These finds did not come from pit-houses where there were only fragments of handmade pots and pottery of the Pastyr's'ke type.

Lukeria Rutkiv's'ka tried to collect contexts of finds of the Kantsyrka type ceramics on the Stetsivka settlement with the aim to allocate remains of the "land-based dwellings of nomads" (Рутковская 1974). This lacked support from other researchers because of the poor conditions of archaeological documentation of the excavations. The collection of ceramics from the settlement was studied by Valentyna Petrashenko to understand the development of the pottery production tradition of Slavs of the Middle Dnieper region (Петрашенко 1992). According to her conclusions, the complex of pottery from the Stetsivka settlement occupy an intermediate position between sites of the 6th – 7th centuries and the 8th – 9th centuries, synchronous with the

Pastyr's'ke hillfort, and can be dated to the 1st half of the 8th century.

Pastyr's'ke (Cherkasy region) – a hillfort of the Scythian culture with a layer of smaller Early Medieval settlement inside (Брайчевский 1951; 1957; Брайчевський 1955; Приходнюк 2005). The fortress was destroyed in the fire which caused the preservation of the full forms of pottery in complexes. Despite this fact, complete vessels of the Kantsyrka type were not found here. This greatly complicates the attribution, given that potters from Pastyr's'ke knew most of the technological methods of Kantsyrka workshops.

Lower part of vessel from a pit-house in sector XIV/1949 (Брайчевський 1955, 70-72, рис. 5/4) differs from pottery of the Pastyr's'ke type with the composition of ceramic paste, the color of firing and the decoration with applied knobbls (**fig. 6/3**). The surface of the vessel had been roughly rubbed with grass. In Alan and Saltiv pottery traditions cooking ware was treated this way. Therefore, this vessel seems only to be an imitation of the medium-sized jugs of the Kantsyrka type (compare: **fig. 1/2, 5, fig. 8/1, 3**). On the other hand, ceramic paste and firing are similar to parts of the pottery found during the excavations of the settlements in the Kantsyrka valley, so the assumption of the manufacture of this vessel in the workshops of Kantsyrka looks quite realistic.

A fragment of light gray clay from the pit-house in sector XII/1949 (Брайчевский 1951, рис. 47; Брайчевський 1955, 69, 70) is well smoothed or slightly polished (**fig. 7/2**). The shape of vessel can be reconstructed as small jug or mug. Its composition of paste differs from Pastyr's'ke type pottery, which usually contains a lot of temper added (sand, grit, grot).

11 small fragments of the same type of paste and firing were found in 1955 in sectors 22 and 23 (Брайчевский 1957). Three of them (**fig. 7/1, 3, 9**) from sector 22 are sherds of big jugs of Kantsyrka type pitchers with typical decoration: wide grooved lines, knobbls, grid of polished lines. The other 3 fragments, from sectors 22 and 23, with polished vertical lines (**fig. 7/ 6, 10, 14**) also match the type of decoration of big and medium-sized Kantsyrka jugs. A fragment of a jug's shoulders from sector 23 (**fig. 7/4**) without decoration, is like a jug from the pit-house in sector XII/1949.

The next group is 4 sherds with engobe from sector 23. One potsherd is decorated with relief polished lines spaced very closely (**fig. 7/5**) is much thinner than others. The size of this vessel could not be large. The surface of vessel was covered with very thin dark grey engobe that Valerii Flyorov calls "the layer for polishing" (Флёров 2000). Three fragments with a polished surface (**fig. 7/7, 8, 12**) were covered with very dark engobe so that originally the surface had to look black. Vessels in this technique were rare in Kantsyrka also.

Oleg Pryhodnyuk considered 4 types of jugs from Pastyr's'ke as the result of the influence from the Kantsyrka center (Приходнюк 2005, 63). Only one of them (Приходнюк 2005, рис. 86/4) repeats the shape of Kantsyrka pitchers. The reconstruction of the second jug (Приходнюк 2005, рис. 95/1) may be wrong if top and bottom belong to different vessels (Приходнюк 2005, фото 44/1, 2). In this case, both fragments would be of jugs of the Kantsyrka type. The shape of one-handed mug (Приходнюк 2005, рис. 93/2, фото 46/1) reminds of the Kantsyrka type mugs (**fig. 2/1, 2**), but is not similar as the ves-

Fig. 7. Fragments of jugs of the Kantsyrka type from Pastyr's'ke: 1, 3, 9, 11, 14 sector 22/1955; 2 pit-house in sector XII/1949; 4-8, 10, 12, 13 sector 23/1955

sel differs in paste and decoration. A pot with thumbed applied strips (Приходнюк 2005, рис. 88/6, фото 36/3) is definitely not of the Kantsyrka production, but its decoration could have been inspired by Kantsyrka type pottery.

The total number of fragments of possible Kantsyrka type pottery is proportionally small in collections from the Pastyr's'ke hillfort. Both pottery production centers definitely existed at the same time, but products of Alan potters were not popular at the Pastyr's'ke hillfort. Which is not surprising, given the high level of development of local pottery making craft. We cannot exclude the possibility that pottery of the Kantsyrka type entered the Pastyr's'ke settlement as containers in local trade.

Early medieval Pastyr's'ke settlement presented with only one layer and one horizon of constructions, so it existed for a short time. Traces of fire throughout the settlement, hoards of jewelry and human remains in the pit houses testify that the fort was captured by the enemy. The biggest problem is that no absolute chronological markers in complexes of Pastyr's'ke have been found yet. The natural scientific methods of chronological analysis were not used either. Dating of the

Pastys'ke settlement is still based on the relative chronology of the ornaments from the hoards.

Olga Shcheglova has divided Slavic hoards of the 6th – 8th centuries from the Dnieper region into two basic groups, concealment of which was caused by different historical events (Щеглова 1990). Hoards of the 1st group (Martynivka horizon) contain digitate and zoomorphic fibulae, belt sets with pseudobuckles and fittings of “heraldic” style, cast massive bracelets, headwear decorations in the shape of spirals etc. Hoards of the 2nd group (Pastys'ke horizon) present other complex of dress ornaments: hammered plate brooches and anthropo-zoomorphic fibulae, hollow bracelets, brazed earrings etc. Dating and analogies of both groups were analyzed in detail by Igor Gavritukhin and Olga Shcheglova (Гавритухин / Обломский 1996; Гавритухин / Щеглова 1996).

Single absolute chronological marker from hoards of the 1st group was found in the Zamostye hoard. A fragment of Byzantine silver dish stamped with a control mark was attributed by Vera Zalesskaya as a stamp of Constantine IV (668–685) (Родинкова 2012), but the stamp is damaged and poorly readable. The dating of analogies is the more reliable now. Belt sets with pseudobuckles in Mala Pereshchepyna and Kelegei found in complexes with coins of Constans II (642-646 and 644-645). Dnieper type digitate fibulae in grave 3 of tomb 186 from the Luchyste cemetery also combined with a coin of Constans II (647-648) (Айбабин / Хайрединова 2008, 39, рис. 22). In grave 6 of tomb 257 from the Eski-Kermen cemetery a digitate fibulae of Dnieper types found with an old broken coin of Heraclius with sons (629-641) (Айбабин 1982, 184-188, рис.10). Analogies allow us to conclude that the event, during which the hoards of the 1st group were hidden, happened in the third quarter of the 7th century.

Later hoards of the 2nd group are mostly found at the Pastys'ke hillfort. The change of heavy-weight dress ornaments to lighter and thinner ones, made in the technique of soldering, coincided with similar processes in the nomad culture observed in complexes from Voznesenka and Glodosy (Комар 2016, 142-146, рис. 2, 3). New types of dress ornaments are being worn by the Slavs of the Dnieper region until the 1st third of the 9th century (Ivahnyky hoard) (Комар 2017). But the upper boundary of the Pastys'ke horizon is determined by the Harivka treasure (Березовець 1952; Приходнюк / Хардаев 1998), synchronous with the Galiat horizon of the North Caucasus Alan culture, during which a mass migration of Alans in the Don basin happened (circa AD 737) (see details: Комар 1999, 121-123, 131-133; 2010, 188-189). Oleg Pryhodnyuk supposed that the Pastys'ke hillfort was also sized in the middle of the 8th century as a result of campaigns and migrations of population of the Saltiv culture (Приходнюк 2005, 78-80). We cannot agree with this – all objects of the Harivka treasure differ from ornaments of the same type from the Pastys'ke hillfort. A set of jewelry from the Harivka treasure takes an intermediate position between Pastys'ke and later Andriyashivka, Fotyvyzh and Ivahnyky hoards. On the other hand, arrowheads of nomad types from the Pastys'ke hillfort (Приходнюк 2005, рис. 29/1-12) are too archaic and too large compared to sets of arrows from early Saltiv graves. This means that the Pastys'ke hillfort was sized no later than the Voznesenka horizon.

Fig. 8. Vessels from Machukhy and Saltiv culture sites: 1-3 Machukhy (Taraniv raven); 4, 5 Mayaki cemetery, complex X (after Маяцкий гончарный комплекс); 6 Novolyumarivka, structure # 7 (after Krasil'nikov 1990)

Finds of fragments of the Kantsyrka type pottery at the Pastyr's'ke hillfort and in nomad complexes from Kelegei, Voznesenka, Zachepylivka, Yasynove belong to the same archaeological period, AD 645-725. The upper limit of the existence of Kantsyrka pottery tradition determined is less confident.

Jugs from a kiln in *Taraniv ravine (Machukhy)* (**fig. 8/1-3**) keep the Kantsyrka type shape and decoration patterns, but the ceramic is harder than the usual sherds from Kantsyrka valley. Its surface was covered by the "layer for polishing" and polished with no relief lines. This fine technique is closer to the traditions of polished vessels of the Saltiv culture (Flërov 1992; Флëров 2000). The biggest jug (**fig. 8/2**) differs from the Saltiv type only by the high neck (Flërov 1992, Taf. 4; 5).

North Caucasus. Alan pottery of Central Caucasus bears the traditional relief decoration until the later stage III of the Mokraya Balka cemetery, synchronous with the Voznesenka horizon (Малашев 2001, рис. 65; Гавритухин 2001, 46-49). Three-handled jugs from the Galiat tomb (Крупнов 1939; Кузнецов 1962, рис. 35) of the following chronological horizon (*terminus post quem* is Arabic dirham, minted in AD 700/701) was decorated in ordinary "Saltiv technique" without relief additions. Synchronous jugs from burial 1 of tomb 5 from Peshchanka had a fully flat surface (Владимиров 1901, рис. 20-21; Кадиева 2014, рис. 1/2-3). It would be possible to conclude that the tradition of Kantsyrka pottery also ended at the stage of Galiat horizon, but archaeological finds from other regions contradict this assumption.

Saltiv culture. Jugs, similar to the Kantsyrka type in form and method of decorating, were produced in the Mayaki settlement on Don river, such as the vessels found in the funeral feast complex X of the

Mayaki catacomb cemetery (Флёрв 1984, 192-193, рис. 26; Flërov 1992, Taf. 4/4, 9/3) (**fig. 8/4, 5**). In an area of the steppe “Bulgarian” variant of the Saltiv culture, a similar technique of decoration with applied strips was observed on pithos vessel from the Tsaryne hillfort (Mayaki) (Михеев 1985, рис. 15, 17) and on a jug from structure # 7 on the Novolymarivka settlement (**fig. 8/6**). Konstantin Krasilnikov concluded that the Novolymarivka jug differs in the technology of production from ordinary pitchers in the region, and therefore should be considered as an import (Красильников 2009, 108, рис. 9/2). Few sherds of rich relief decorated pottery from the citadel of Sarkel fortress (build after AD 836) are of the orange firing, Mihail Artamonov considered them also as imports (Артамонов 1958, 43, рис. 31). Svetlana Pletnyova supposed that such vessels could be imported from Middle Asia (Плетнёва 1959, 253; рис. 36/1). Another rare fragment of jar with small bumps on the neck differs from Kantsyrka type jugs in shape (Плетнёва 1959, 253, рис. 3). We can only state that at the stage of the Saltiv culture the technique of relief decoration of pottery evolved further, and the closest to the Kantsyrka pottery making traditions were kept until the 9th century by a small group of Alan potters in the Don region.

Bulgaria. The hypothesis of the transfer of Kantsyrka pottery traditions (in any form) to the Danube region by Bulgarian tribes of the Asparukh’s Unnogundur union after AD 681 is supported by many Bulgarian archaeologists. However, at the moment it cannot be illustrated by any real find of fragments of Kantsyrka type pottery in Bulgaria.

Boris Borisov published a photo of the jar from Mayaki settlement (**fig. 8/5**) as a vessel from Bdintsi (Борисов 2011, табл. 7/в), which is an obvious mistake. A jug from the cremation grave 76 of the Bdintsi cemetery (Въжарова 1976, 161-163, обр. 102/6) only imitates the shape of North Caucasian Alan three-handled jugs (**fig. 9/1**). The vessel is made of yellow clay covered with dirty gray engobe. It is decorated with applied arc-shaped strips and knobs remnant of the big and middle-sized jugs of the Kantsyrka type (**fig. 1/1, 6, fig. 8/1**), but there are no polishing or grids of polished lines. An even more distant imitation was found in the inhumation grave 261 from the Balchik cemetery (Дончева-Петкова et al. 2016, 220, таб. XXXVIII, CCXLIII/1). The Balchik jug differs with the shape of its neck and the color of firing (**fig. 9/2**). Both burials did not contain narrowly dated artifacts. A jug from the grave 55 of the Kyulevcha cemetery was decorated with small knobbls on body (Въжарова 1976, обр. 69/2). This grave was dated by the type of Late Avar cheek bits and also by bone fasteners, found in nomad graves of the Volga region, dated no earlier than the mid-8th century (Богачёв / Мышкин 1995, рис. 4/13; Путешествие ибн-Фадлана 2016, 254-254, кат. 183).

Jugs from Novi Pazar grave 22 (Станчев / Иванов 1958, таб. XX) and Plachidol (Борисов 2011, табл. 6/к) were decorated with arcs of notches. They resembles patterns of the Kantsyrka decoration of jugs, but, neither the form or the technology of manufacturing these vessels was similar to the Kantsyrka type pottery.

The main question is what did cause the production of such imitations in Bulgaria: the weak memory of the old tradition or the synchronous fashion of using similar jugs by nomads of the Northern Black Sea region?

Fig. 9. Jugs with relief decoration from Bulgaria: 1 Bdintsi, grave 76; 2 Balchik, grave 261; 3 Novi Pazar, grave 36; 4 Dibich, grave 1; 5 Troshevo, grave 360; 6 Kyulevcha, grave 20; 7 Pliska, barrow XXXIII

Three-handled jugs in the ceramic complex of the Danube Bulgars are presented with quite a homogeneous type of high neck and oinochoe-shaped spout (Дончева-Петкова 1977, 72-74, тип IVБ; Fiedler 1992, 143, type FXIII/2; Рашев 2008, 181, обр. 67, таб. CX/7, CXI/1, 3-8, type B1). The side handles are considered as decorative, and sometimes they do not even have holes (**fig. 9/3**). Rarely jugs were polished and decorated with polished lines (**fig. 9/4**); this variant is similar to the North Caucasian jug of the first half of the 8th century from Peshchanka (Владимиров 1901, рис. 20). The latest group of jugs found in a secret passage of the “Khan Krum palace” (Рашев 2008, CXI/1, 3-8) is not polished.

A jug from grave 58 of the Kyulevcha cemetery, decorated with applied knobs on either side of spout (Въжарова 1976, обр. 71/2), is of the Saltiv jugs shape but its decoration is not typical. A unique three-legged pitcher from Istria, decorated with multiple knobs, is also close to Saltiv jugs (Fiedler 1992, Taf. 10/6). Quite a different tradition is represented by jugs with knobs from grave 360 of the Troshevo cemetery (**fig. 9/5**) and Pliska grave XXXIII (**fig. 8/7**). They are definitely not related to either the Saltiv or Kantsyrka pottery traditions, as there was also a jug of yellow paste from grave 20 of the Kyulevcha cemetery, decorated with applied strips (**fig. 9/6**).

Less obvious, but no less interesting, are the parallels that come

from the Novi Pazar cemetery. Two jugs (**fig. 10/1, 4**) from grave 33 (Станчев / Иванов 1958, таб. XI) were traditionally regarded as the earliest vessels of the Danube Proto-Bulgarians (Дончева-Петкова 1977, 70-73, 173-175; Dončeva-Petkova 1990, Abb. 2; Fiedler 1992, B.3; Христова 2011, 54). A jug of gray firing with a long spout of the North Caucasian type is decorated with wide vertical polished lines on the neck and with relief zigzags on the body (**fig. 10/1, 1a**). Vertical polished lines on the neck are often found on Kantsyrka type jugs (**fig. 1/3, fig. 6/1b, fig. 8/1-3**). Technique of relief zigzags were used sometimes by Kantsyrka potters for decorating of grooves on the neck of jugs (**fig. 3/8**), but more often they did it with the help of toothed tool (**fig. 4/3, fig. 5/4**). Herringbone décor on Novi Pazar gray polished vessels (**fig. 10/1b-3a**) was made with blunt-pointed tool one line after another. Arc-shaped décor on vessel from grave 22 (Станчев / Иванов 1958, таб. XX) and Plachidol (Борисов 2011, табл. 6/к) also was made with blunt-pointed tool. It seems that potters who made Novi Pazar vessels were familiar with the patterns of decoration of the Alanian vessels of North Caucasus, but they used them in their own way.

A toothed tool or an even cogwheel was used for decorating the orange polished jug from the Novi Pazar grave 33 (**fig. 10/4**). A polished jug of orange firing with zigzags décor was also found in cremation grave 5 of the Khitovo cemetery (**fig. 10/5**). Jugs have nothing in common with the Avar orange vessels, either in form or in ornamentation, the same as orange and red polished jugs from the Topola cemetery. Similar polished orange pottery to the east of Danube river usually date to 2nd half of the 9th – 10th centuries due to the prevalence in late layers of the Sarkel fortress (Флëров 1976) and the Tankeevka cemetery in Volga Bulgaria (Хлебникова 1984, 58-62). Only five orange vessels were found in the earlier Bol'shyye Tarkhany cemetery (late 8th – 9th centuries) of Volga Bulgarians (Генинг / Халиков 1964, 36). The Khitovo cemetery differs from other cemeteries of the region in funeral rites, namely by the domination of the orientation of inhumation graves to the east (Йотов 1989).

Stefka Angelova and Lydmila Doncheva-Petkova supposed that the Proto-Bulgarian tribes of Asparukh came to the territory of Bulgaria with the fully completed tradition of the production of polished pottery (Ангелова / Дончева-Петкова 1990). The variety of the shape of vessels, their ornamentation and production techniques show that different North Caucasian groups of the population with different pottery traditions were involved in the migration of the Bulgars. This complicates the problem of the initial region of origin of Proto-Bulgarians ceramic traditions. Only one of these groups was familiar with products of Alan potters of the Kantsyrka tradition, which was not continued further in Bulgaria.

Vessels resembling some Kantsyrka elements in the decoration and design of jugs were found in graves of three Bulgarian cemeteries: Bdintsi, Balchik and Kyulevcha. Two of them are also distinguished by the presence of burials with artifacts, usually dated to 7th century. In the Kyulevcha cemetery it is grave 84-A with a bronze B-shaped buckle (repository of the National Archaeological Institute with Museum at Sofia) and grave 78 with a hollow cross (Въжарова 1976, обр. 75/7; pressed analogy was in the tomb of 8th century of the Baklynskiy Ovrage

cemetery in Crimea – Айбабин / Юрочкин 1995, рис. 8/8). An iron V-shaped buckle was also found in the Balchik grave 243 (Дончева-Петкова et al. 2016, таб. LI, ССХIV); other “7th century” chronological markers from this cemetery are not correct and should be discussed separately (Коматарова-Балинова 2018, 59-61). These two cemeteries belong to the earliest stage of the emergence of bi-ritual cemeteries of Proto-Bulgarians. The earliest dated grave from the Bdintsi cemetery, grave 31 (Въжарова 1976, обр. 95), belongs to the same horizon as the Kabiyuk grave (Тотев / Пелевина 2010; 2011; Рашев et al. 2014).

Whatever the mechanism of the influence of Kantsyrka pottery traditions on Danubian Bulgars, it is recorded in burials later than AD 681 and can be traced at least to the middle of the 8th century. This corresponds to chronological indications of complexes from the Dnieper region.

If we summarize the data on the archaeological dating of Kantsyrka type pottery from nomad complexes and Slavic settlements of the Dnieper region, the *terminus post quem* can be determined by coins from Kelegei, minted in AD 644/645. The upper limit is determined by the similarity of the manufacturing technique of big jugs from Taraniv ravine (Machukhy) to three-handled jugs of the Saltiv culture and also by the production of derivatives of Kantsyrka type jugs at the Mayaki settlement. Workshops of the Kantsyrka circle could function in the Dnieper area until the moment of migration of the Saltiv culture population in the Don basin after AD 737 (or circa AD 740). Therefore, a “wide” archaeological date of Kantsyrka type pottery can be set within the framework of AD 645-740.

VERIFICATION OF ARCHAEO-MAGNETIC DATING

In 1968 Grygoriy Zagniy started to collect samples for archaeomagnetic measurements from archaeological sites in Ukraine and Moldova. The first results, based on measurements of 39 objects, were published by Oleg Rusakov and Grygoriy Zagniy in 1973 (Rusakov / Zagniy 1973a; 1973b). The next stage of research was presented in the manuscript of the report for a five-year research period (1973-1977), where measurements of 146 objects from sites of Ukraine and Moldova were used to summarize trends of secular variation in declination, inclination and intensity of the Earth’s magnetic field in historic time (Русаков / Загний 1977). Results and methods were summarized in the thesis of Grygoriy Zagniy (1981) and in the monograph of Grygoriy Zagniy and Oleg Rusakov (Загний / Русаков 1982). Later Grygoriy Zagniy provided his data for a catalog of archaeomagnetic dating, edited by Seraphima Burlatskaya (Бурлацкая 1986).

Three kilns from the Lyubymivka settlement were sampled by Grygoriy Zagniy in 1968, 1969, 1970 and coded with numbers 18, 45, 100. According to Alla Smilenko, codes correspond to kilns # 12, 13, 17 (Сміленко 1975, 155; Smilenko 1990, 323). Alla Smilenko changed field numbers of kilns in her monograph, and kiln with new number “12” (field # 18) from the workshop VIII (**fig. 10**) was the latest excavated in 1970. Grygoriy Zagniy took samples for archaeomagnetic dating from this kiln also in 1970, as it was recorded in the field report (Сміленко 1970, 2). Dates of archaeological discovery of kilns # 13 and # 17 do not match the years of sampling for archaeomagnetic dating, but there is no contradiction with the information of Alla Smilenko.

Fig. 10. Jugs with relief decoration from Bulgaria: 1, 4 Novi Pazar, grave 33; 2 Novi Pazar, grave 16; 3 Novi Pazar, grave 9; 5 Khitovo, grave 5

Kiln # 13 (field # 12) from the workshop VII was studied in 1964, but re-excavated in 1968. Kiln # 17 (field # 16) from the workshop XI was excavated in 1968 and unearthed again in 1969. Thus, codes of Grygoriy Zagniy correspond to following objects: code 18 – kiln # 13 (field # 12/1964); code 45 – kiln # 17 (field # 16/1968); code 100 – kiln # 12 (field # 18/1970).

The first version of archaeomagnetic dating, proposed for kilns # 13 and 16, was the “VI century AD” (Rusakov / Zagniy 1973a, 154; 1973b, 282). The dating was changed for next works: kilns # 12 and # 17 were dated to the 7th century, and kiln # 13 – to the 8th century (Русаков / Загний 1977, # 68, 74, 76; Загний / Русаков 1982, 124, 125, # 67, 73, 75). There were also changes in archaeomagnetic data values at each stage of the study, based on a larger number of samples measured (**table 1**). Dating of kilns, published by Alla Smilenko with a reference to Grygoriy Zagniy (Сміленко 1975, 155), most likely, reflected some intermediate stage in the study.

The presence of a chronological error in the local archaeomagnetic curve for the territory of Ukraine and Moldova, created by Grygoriy Zagniy and Oleg Rusakov, is indicated by the dating of two objects from the Gorosheva settlement of the Praga culture and oven of the pit-house # 2 from the Khodosivka settlement of the Volyntseve culture. Two objects of the Praga culture from Gorosheva (archaeological date: 6th – 7th centuries AD) (Баран / Пачкова 1975) were dated by Grygoriy

Zagniy and Oleg Rusakov to the 5th century AD, and an object of the Volyntseve culture from Khodosivka (archaeological date: 8th century AD) (Сухобоків 1977) was dated to the 6th century (Русаков / Загний 1977, # 65-67; Загний / Русаков 1982, 124, # 64-66).

Mentioned archaeological objects cannot be re-examined in field and the samples collected earlier are not preserved. In order to verify the archaeomagnetic dating of two pit-houses from the Khodosivka settlement (codes 144, 145) using old data of Grygoriy Zagniy, the analysis of data was conducted with help of the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* software and three global models: ARCH3K.1, SHA.DIF.14K and CALS3K.3 (Pavón-Carrasco et al. 2011). As in the case of Kantsyrka kilns, archaeomagnetic data was presented in several versions. The first version of data (1977) included only declination and inclination values, the later version (1986) added field intensity values. The new results of archaeomagnetic dating for pit-houses # 1 and # 2 from the Khodosivka settlement, made by the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* software, were in good agreement with archaeological date in all three used models. A comparison showed that the later version of the Grygoriy Zagniy's data (1986) was more consistent with archaeological dating. The statement of the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* developers, that SHA.DIF.14K model produces in average a more accurate than CALS3K.3 match with archaeological dates for the European sites and very close results to ARCH3K.1 model, was also verified and confirmed in this example. "Problematic dating" of the Khodosivka pit-house # 2 (code 145) after verification using the SHA.DIF.14K model was set within an acceptable framework (95% probability) of the AD 702-802 (Комар 2018).

The second "problematic" example mentioned above is the oven (code 103) and the "dryer-stove" (code 106) inside of one pit-dwelling from Gorosheva settlement. The relative chronological position of the Kantsyrka kilns in the scheme of Grygoriy Zagniy and Oleg Rusakov was much later than the objects from Gorosheva (up to two or three centuries). The expected archaeological difference in the date cannot be so great. Chronological interpretation of archaeomagnetic data on Gorosheva objects using the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* and SHA.DIF.14K model gives a new date (confidence = 95%): oven – AD 586-718: "dryer-stove" – AD 563-699. The Praga culture pottery from complexes of the settlement was dated to the same time, and a "Danubian" bow fibula from the cultural layer was dated to the 7th century AD (Баран / Пачкова 1975, 93-95; Гавритухин 1991, 130-131). As we see, improvement of analysis tools and databases allow to verify old archaeomagnetic dating with quite satisfactory results.

The procedure for the verification of archaeomagnetic dating of Kantsyrka kilns is a little harder because of the choice to use the most balanced version of data. In the example with objects of the Volyntseve culture from the Khodosivka settlement, the 1973 version does not exist, and version of data published in 1986 included values of inclination and declination calculated on a smaller number of samples accepted compared with the 1977 version. This meant using the procedure to exclude extreme values. In the example of Kantsyrka kilns the situation is different: the 1986 data version takes into account the maximum number of samples, while the excluding procedure was applied for kiln 17 (code 45) in the version of 1977 compared with the

Table 1

Object	Code	Latitude	Longitude	Number of samples	I	D	α_{95}	F/F_0	α	F_0	References
Kiln 13	18	48.5	35.0	19	69.0	344.0	0.4			48	Rusakov / Zagniy 1973a
Kiln 13	18	48.5	35.0	2				1.35	0.03		Rusakov / Zagniy 1973b
Kiln 13	18	48.0	35.0	22	67.0	344.0	0.5				Русаков / Загний 1977
Kiln 13	18	48.2	34.9	23	68.0	343.5	0.5				Бурлацкая 1986
Kiln 13	18	48.2	34.9	7				1.35	0.03		Бурлацкая 1986
Kiln 14	45	48.5	35.0	27	70.5	345.5	0.3				Rusakov / Zagniy 1973a
Kiln 14	45	48.5	35.0	4				1.4	0.04		Rusakov / Zagniy 1973b
Kiln 14	45	48.0	35.0	18	69.0	345.5	0.5				Русаков / Загний 1977
Kiln 14	45	48.2	34.9	24	71.0	346.5	0.7				Бурлацкая 1986
Kiln 14	45	48.2	34.9	8				1.29	0.06		Бурлацкая 1986
Kiln 18	100	48.0	35.0	16	69.5	347.0	0.7				Русаков / Загний 1977
Kiln 18	100	48.2	34.9	32	72	351	1.2				Бурлацкая 1986
Kiln 18	100	48.2	34.9	6				1.4	0.02		Бурлацкая 1986

1973 version (**table 1**). Diary schedule records of Grygoriy Zagniy are now unavailable, so it is not possible to determine how significant the dispersion of initial data was. This made it necessary to verify all three versions of data to see which of them would be closest to archaeological dates. Since the 1977 version of data does not include values on intensity of the field, the “combined” version is added. It takes data on declination and inclination from the 1977 version and intensity values from the 1986 version.

The results of a chronological interpretation of all versions of data using the *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating* and ARCH3K.1, SHA.DIF.14K, CALS3K.3 models are presented in **table 2**. There is an obvious tendency that with each recalculation of data by Grygoriy Zagniy, dating had been changed toward the younger age of objects. Analysis of graphs (**fig. 11**) demonstrates that the main cause was the change in the values of inclination.

The 1986 version of data produces barely acceptable chronological frames for kiln 12 (code 100) in ARCH3K.1 and SHA.DIF.14K models. Less precise CALS3K.3 model includes frames of archaeological date in this case due to the traditionally wider span of archaeomagnetic dating (caused by the use of lake sediment data). A “combined” version of data (1977/1986) for the kiln 12 is agrees much better with the archaeological dating, although it is based on half the number of samples accepted (**fig. 13/3**). Archaeomagnetic dating of other kilns in “combined” version of the data is in good agreement with archaeological dating (**fig. 13/1, 2**) and allows it to be more balanced.

In the case of kiln 13 all three models gave very close time intervals as a result, while in the chronological interpretation of data on kilns 12 and 17 the difference is quite discernible (**table 2, fig. 12**). The reason is a good agreement of declination, inclination, and intensity graphs of kiln 13 (**fig. 11/1**) and a more complicated correlation of graphs for kilns 12 and 17 (**fig. 11/2, 3**). Interpreting the non-standard combination of data, each of models solves a problem individually. All three kilns are practically synchronous in the CALS3K.3 model, with the possibility of later dates for kilns 12 and 17 (**fig. 12/c**). ARCH3K.1 and SHA.DIF.14K models allocate kiln 13 as earlier, while kilns 12 and 17

Table 2

Object	Code	Data ver- sion	ARCH3K.1		SHA.DIF.14K		CAL3K.3		Archaeol. date
			σ 95%	σ 65%	σ 95%	σ 65%	σ 95%	σ 65%	
Kiln 13	18	1973	655-751	698-737	677-744	696-720	626-727	657-697	645-740
		1977	633-745	665-725	622-732	666-721	611-744	649-699	645-740
		1986	647-743	686-731	658-735	688-720	626-720	656-695	645-740
		comb.*	634-736	666-722	634-723	669-713	621-721	653-696	645-740
Kiln 17	45	1973	650-770	712-752	685-777	712-743	618-758 771-801	650-706	645-740
		1977	673-788	720-764	707-812	721-770	627-806	647-711	645-740
		1986	696-795	725-767	718-821	730-779	632-749 764-840	651-713	645-740
		comb.*	654-762	699-744	691-770	710-741	618-748 788-801	656-701	645-740
Kiln 12	100	1977	698-803	734-775	725-828	740-798	629-822	648-720 777-801	645-740
		1986	731-849	747-803	729-798 801-858	733-773 833-851	664-883	782-859	645-740
		comb.*	695-782	725-755	704-769	720-746	626-819	647-718	645-740

* Combines declination and inclination values of the 1977 version and intensity values of the 1986 version

Fig. 11. Plan of the Lyubymivka settlement (after Сміленко 1975, with corrections)

are almost synchronous (fig. 12/a, s).

The chronological result, produced by the Bayesian statistics in the form of a numeric record (table 2), should be perceived by archaeologists as a provisional². At the moment, the basis of archaeomagnetic databases is a number of archaeological objects with a quite broad dating, recorded like “8th century AD” = “750±50”, with smaller admixture

² Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating and syntetic models which it operates with also take into account the moment of uncertainty, thus the received date on identical data slightly differs in numerical expression after each reboot of the software.

Fig. 12. Archaeomagnetic dating of kilns from the Lybymivka settlement with *Matlab tool for archaeomagnetic dating*, SHA. DIF.14K: 1 kiln 13; 2 kiln 17; 3 kiln 12

of more accurately dated objects. Graphs demonstrate that archaeomagnetic dating of kilns 12 and 17 is mostly determined by inclination values, specific for objects of the 8th – 9th centuries AD (800 ± 100 or later) (fig. 11/2, 3), while the date of kiln 13 is determined by values, specific for objects dated to the 700 ± 50 (fig. 11/1). The result of archaeomagnetic dating will be improved in process of further development of the analysis tools and databases. On the other hand, we must admit that the modern verification of the archaeomagnetic dating of samples collected and measured in 1968-1981 gave a fully acceptable result in good agreement with archaeological dates.

CONCLUSIONS

Alan potters from Kantsyrka valley produced vessels for nomads of the Lower Dnieper region in the second half of the 7th – early 8th centuries AD. They also sold pitchers to some groups of Slavic population of the late Pen'kivka culture of the Middle Dnieper area. And even the inhabitants of the Pastyrskye hillfort (last third of the 7th – early 8th centuries AD) with the developed own pottery production also used Kantsyrka jugs.

Archaeomagnetic dates were obtained for kilns of three pottery workshops (# VII, VIII, XI) of the Lyubymivka settlement in Kantsyrka valley. The earliest of the three workshops was workshop VII with kiln 13 (circa AD 634-723). A building of the workshop burned (Сміленко 1975, 126-129), but the pit-house of the nearest workshop VIII with kiln 12 (circa AD 704-769) appeared nearby. Kiln 17 (circa AD 691-770) of the workshop XI heated for the last time almost synchronously to kiln 12 (fig. 13/2, 3).

Alla Smilenko supposed that all eastern part of workshops (X-XII) (fig. 10) was burned at the same time with workshop VII as the result of enemy attack (Сміленко 1975, 132-140, 157). This hypothesis cannot be supported. The analysis of field reports shows that there were no remains of burned wooden constructions and traces of fire throughout the area of buildings as it was in workshop VII. A burned spot on the floor of the pit-house 5 (workshop XI) was located near the hearth (possibly, a place for charcoals), and 3 fragments of the human (?) parietal bone were found in the pit-house 5 in different places at various depths, which indicates their entry into the pit with filling soil. These markers are not enough either for the assertion of the widespread fire in the settlement, nor for the enemies' attack. Pottery production was specially located in such valleys with streams because of fire hazard. The Lyubymivka settlement continued to exist further after the fire in the workshop VII and it was only abandoned by its inhabitants circa AD 730-740, according to verified archaeomagnetic

Fig. 13. Archaeomagnetic dating of kilns from the Lyubymivka settlement in comparison with the frames of archaeological dating: **a** ARCH3K.1; **c** CALS3K.3; **s** SHA.DIF.14K; 1 kiln 13; 2 kiln 17; 3 kiln 12

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Айбабин, А. И. 2013. Археологическое наследие хазар времени создания каганата. – Материалы и исследования по археологии, истории и этнографии Таврии 18, 277-315.

Айбабин, А. И. 1999. Этническая

история ранневизантийского Крыма. Симферополь.

Айбабин, А. И. 1991. Келегейское погребение военного вождя. In: Проблемы на прабългарската история и култура 2. София. 28-35.

Айбабин, А. И. 1985. Погребение

хазарского воина. – Советская археология 3, 191-205.

Айбабин, А. И. 1982. Погребения конца VII – первой половины VIII в. в Крыму. In: Амброс, А. К. / Эрдели, И. Ф. (eds.). Древности эпохи великого переселения народов. Москва. 165-192.

- Айбабин, А. И. / Хайрединова, Э. А.* 2008. Могильник у села Лучистое. Раскопки 1977, 1982–1984 годов. Т. 1. Киев.
- Айбабин, А. И. / Юрочкин, В. Ю.* 1995. Могильник «Баклинский овраг» (по материалам раскопок 1992-1993 г.). In: Могаричев, И. М. / Храпунов, И. Н. (eds.). Проблемы археологии древнего и средневекового Крыма. Симферополь. 125-135.
- Амброз, А. К.* 1981. Восточноевропейские и среднеазиатские степи V – первой половины VIII в. In: Плетнёва, С. А. (ed.). Степи Евразии в эпоху средневековья. Москва. 10-23.
- Ангелова, С. / Дончева-Петкова, Л.* 1990. Традиции в прабългарската излъскана керамика. – Добруджа 7, 62-69.
- Артамонов, М. И.* 1958. Саркел-Белая Вежа. – Материалы и исследования по археологии СССР 62, 7-84.
- Атавин, А. Г. / Паромов, Я. М.* 1991. Болгарское погребение с золотым поясным набором из Нижнего Прикубанья. In: Абрамов, А. П. / Гавритухин, И. О. / Паромов, Я. М. / Эрлих, В. Р. (eds.). Древности Северного Кавказа и Причерноморья. Москва. 151-155.
- Атанасов, Г. Г.* 2017. Новый владетельский центр кагана Кубрата на Среднем Днепре. In: Крадин, Н. Н. / Ситдииков, А. Г. (eds.). Между Востоком и Западом: движение культур, технологий и империй. (III Международный конгресс средневековой археологии евразийских степей). Владивосток. 20-27.
- Атанасов, Г.* 2015. Първостроителите на българската държавност (619-721). София.
- Баран, В. Д. / Пачкова, С. П.* 1975. Славянское поселение у с. Горошева на Днестре. – Археология 18, 87-95.
- Березовец, Д. Т.* 1952. Харівський
- скарб. – Археологія 6, 109-119.
- Білецький, А. В.* 2012. Вознесенське поховання: проблема інтерпретації. In: Ковальова, І.Ф. (ed.). Проблеми археології Подніпров'я. Дніпропетровськ. 40-49.
- Білецький, А. / Шаповалов, Г.* 2014. Вознесенський (Кічкаський) «скарб» – поховання-спалення X ст. – Наукові студії 7, 285-304.
- Богачёв, А. В. / Мышкин, В. Н.* 1995. Раннеболгарский курган у с. Осиновка. In: Матвеева, Г. И. (ed.). Средневековые памятники Поволжья. Самара. 65-75.
- Борисов, Б. Д.* 2011. Керамика дунайской Болгарии (VIII–X вв.). In: Хузин, Ф. Ш. (ed.). Болгарский форум I. Материалы Международного Болгарского Форума (19-21 июня 2010 г., Болгар) (= Археология евразийских степей 12). Казань. 35-45.
- Брайчевська, А. Т.* 1961. Розкопки гончарського горна в балці Канцирка в 1955 р. – Археологія 13, 114-118.
- Брайчевский, М. Ю.* 1957. Исследование Пастырского городища в 1955 г. – Краткие сообщения Института археологии АН УССР 7, 94-96.
- Брайчевський, М. Ю.* 1955. Нові розкопки на Пастырському городищі. – Археологічні пам'ятки УРСР 5, 67-76.
- Брайчевский, М. Ю.* 1951. Работы на Пастырском городище в 1949 г. – Краткие сообщения Института истории материальной культуры 36, 155-164.
- Бубенок, О. Б.* 2005. Протоболгары і сармато-алани наприкінці V–VII ст. – Східний світ 4, 5-19.
- Бурлацкая, С. П. (ed.)* 1986. Археомангнитные определения элементов геомагнитного поля. Мировые данные. Материалы Мирового центра данных. Москва.
- Владимиров, И. А.* 1901. Раскопки на «Песчанке». In: Отчёт Императорской археологической комиссии за 1898 г. Санкт-Петербург. 124-135.
- Володарець-Урбанович, Я. В.* 2014а. Гончарний посуд VII — першої половини IX ст. в лісостепу України. Автореферат дисертації кандидата історичних наук. Київ.
- Володарець-Урбанович, Я. В.* 2014б. Проблеми вивчення гончарних осередків типу балки Канцерка. – Археологія 2, 51-59.
- Володарець-Урбанович, Я. В.* 2012. Хронология бытования канцерской гончарной посуды. In: Щеглова, О.А. / Горюнова, В. М. (eds.). Славяне Восточной Европы накануне образования Древнерусского государства: Материалы Международной конференции, посвященной 110-летию со дня рождения И. И. Ляпушкина (1902–1968) (3-5 декабря 2012 г. Санкт-Петербург). Санкт-Петербург. 94-97.
- Володарець-Урбанович, Я. В. / Скиба, А. В.* 2011. Гончарний посуд VII-VIII ст. на Півдні Східної Європи. – Археологія 2, 34-46.
- Въжарова, Ж. Н.* 1976. Славяни и прабългари (по данни на некрополите от VI-XI в. на територията на България). София.
- Гавритухин, И. О.* 2005. Хронология эпохи становления Хазарского каганата (элементы ременной гарнитуры). In: Петрухин, В. / Москович, В. / Федорчук, А. / Кулик, А. / Шапира, Д. (eds.). Хазары (= Евреи и славяне 16). Москва / Иерусалим. 378-426.
- Гавритухин, И. О.* 2001. Периодизация раннесредневековых древностей Кисловодской котловины на основе керамики в свете изучения изделий из металла. In: Малашев, В. Ю. (ed.). Керамика раннесредневекового могильника Мокрая Балка. Москва. 40-49.
- Гавритухин, И. О.* 1991. Пальчатые

- фибулы пражских памятников Поднепровья. – In: Абрамов, А. П. / Гавритухин, И. О. / Паромов, Я. М. / Эрлих, В. Р. (eds.). Древности Северного Кавказа и Причерноморья. Москва. 127-141.
- Гавритухин, И. О. / Обломский, А. М. 1996. Гапоновский клад и его культурно-исторический контекст. Раннеславянский мир 3. Москва.
- Гавритухин, И. О. / Щеглова, О. А. 1996. Группы днепровских раннесредневековых кладов. In: Гавритухин, И. О. / Обломский, А. М. Гапоновский клад и его культурно-исторический контекст (= Раннеславянский мир 3). Москва. 53-57.
- Генинг, В. Ф. / Халиков, А. Х. 1964. Ранние болгары на Волге: Больше-Тарханский могильник. Москва.
- Горюнов, Е. А. 1987. Пеньковская и салтовская культуры в Среднем Поднепровье. – Краткие сообщения Института археологии АН СССР 190, 3-7.
- Гринченко, В. А. 1950. Пам'ятка VIII ст. коло с. Вознесенки на Запоріжжі. – Археологія 3, 37-63.
- Гринченко, В. А. 1937. Пам'ятник VIII в. відкритий біля с. Вознесенки на Запоріжжі 1930 р. – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11, # Г/1.
- Гринченко, В. А. 1931. Щоденник розкопів на балці Канцірка. – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 11, # Г/7.
- Гюзелев, В. 1979. Икономическо развитие, социална структура и форми на социална и политическа организация на прабългарите до образуването на българската държава (IV-VII в.). – Археологія 4, 12-22.
- Димитров, Д. 1987. Прабългарите по Северното и Западното Черноморие. Варна.
- Дніпрельстанівська археологічна експедиція 1931. – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 18, # 130.
- Дончева-Петкова, Л. 1977. Българска битова керамика през ранното средновековие. София.
- Дончева-Петкова, Л. / Апостолов, К. / Русева, В. 2016. Прабългарският некропол при Балчик. София.
- Загний, Г. Ф. 1979. Структура археологических вариаций геомагнитного поля на Украине и в Молдавии за последние 5500 лет: Автореферат диссертации канд. физ.-мат. наук. Киев.
- Загний, Г. Ф. / Русаков, О. М. 1982. Археологические вариации геомагнитного поля юго-запада СССР. Киев.
- Йотов, В. 1989. Раннобългарски некропол при с. Хитово, Толбухински окръг. In: Проблеми на прабългарската история и култура 1. София. 221-230.
- Кадиева, А. А. 2014. Погребальный комплекс, включающий пояс с изображениями фантастических животных, из могильника Песчанка в верховьях реки Нальчик (раскопки И. А. Владимировой). In: Бгажноков, Б. Х. / Фоменко, В. А. (eds.) Древняя и средневековая культура адыгов. Нальчи. 54-75
- Казанский, М. М. 2014. Археологическая ситуация в Среднем Поднепровье в VII в. In: Обломский А. В. (ред.). Проблемы взаимодействия населения Восточной Европы в эпоху Великого переселения народов. (Раннеславянский мир 15). Москва. 45-137.
- Комар, О. В. 2018. Археологічне та археомагнітне датування волинцевських комплексів Ходосівського поселення. – Археологія і давня історія України 28, 3, 168-191.
- Комар, А. В. 2017. Ивахниковский клад (время сокрытия и культурные связи комплекса). – Stratum plus 5, 113-131.
- Комар, А. 2016. Днепровские пластинчатые фибулы: истоки формы и стиля. In: Chudzińska, B. / Wojenka, M. / Wołoszyn, M. (eds.). Od Bachorza do Światowida ze Zbrucza: tworzenie się słowiańskiej Europy w ujęciu źródłoznaczym: księga jubileuszowa Profesora Michała Parczewskiego. Kraków / Rzeszów. 137-149.
- Комар, А. В. 2014. Место гибели князя Святослава: поиски, легенды, гипотезы, мистификации. – Stratum plus 5, 235-256.
- Комар, А. В. 2013. Кочевники восточноевропейских степей второй половины VI – первой половины VIII в. In: Досымбаева, А. / Жолдасбеков, М. (eds.). Западный Тюркский каганат. Астана. 671-737.
- Комар, А. В. 2010. К дискуссии о хронологии раннесредневековых кочевнических памятников Среднего Поволжья. In: Сташенков, Д. А. (ed.). Культуры евразийских степей второй половины I тысячелетия н.э. (вопросы меэтнических контактов и межкультурного взаимодействия). Самара. 169-206.
- Комар, А. В. 2008. Наследие Западнотюркского каганата в Восточной Европе. In: Івакін, Г. Ю. (ed.). Збірка праць на пошану дійсного члена Національної академії наук України Петра Петровича Толочка з нагоди його 70-річчя. Київ. 288-300.
- Комар, А. В. 2006. Перещепинский комплекс в контексте основных проблем истории и культуры кочевников Восточной Европы VII – начала VIII в. – Степи Европы в эпоху средневековья 5, 7-244.
- Комар, А. В. 1999. Предсалтовские и раннесалтовские горизонты Восточной Европы. – Vita Antiqua 2, 111-136.
- Комар, А. В. / Хардаев, В. М. 2012. Зачепиловский (“Новосанжарский”) комплекс рубежа VII-VIII вв. – Степи Европы в эпоху средневековья 9, 243-296.

- Коматарова-Балинова, Е. 2018. „Прабългарите“ при Балчик и номадите в полето на „прабългарската“ археология. – Приноси към българската археология 8, 47-92.
- Красильников, К. И. 2009. Лощеная керамика из степного массива салтово-маяцкой культуры (типология, технология, орнаментика, клейма). – Степи Европы в эпоху средневековья 7, 99-152.
- Крупнов, Е. И. 1938. Галиатский могильник, как источник по истории алан-оссов. – Вестник древней истории 2, 113-122.
- Кузнецов, В. А. 1962. Аланские племена Северного Кавказа. – Материалы и исследования по археологии СССР 106, 1-164.
- Малашев, В. Ю. 2001. Керамика раннесредневекового могильника Мокрая Балка. Москва.
- Мацулевич, Л. А. 1959. Войсковой знак V в. – Византийский Временник 16, 183-205.
- Маяцкий гончарный комплекс. Available at: <http://www.divnogor.ru/sights/archeology/srednevekovje/goncharnyj>
- Михеев, В. К. 1985. Подонье в составе Хазарского каганата. Харьков.
- Миллер, М. 1951. Могила князя Святослава. Вінніпег.
- Миллер, М. 1947. Ще за могилу князя Святослава. – Чорноморський збірник 10, 57-60.
- Миллер, М. 1946. Могила князя Святослава. Женева.
- Мінаєва, Т. М. 1961. Кераміка балки Канцирка в світлі археологічних досліджень на Північному Кавказі. – Археологія 13, 119-128.
- Обломский, А. М. 2012. Структура населения Лесостепного Поднепровья в VII в. н.э. In: Мельникова, Е. А. (ред.). Древнейшие государства Восточной Европы. Москва. 10-33.
- Петрашенко, В. О. 1992. Слов'янська кераміка VIII-IX ст. Правобережжя Середнього Подніпров'я. Київ.
- Петров, В. П. 1963. Стецовка, поселение третьей четверти I тысячелетия н.э. – Материалы и исследования по археологии СССР 108, 209-233.
- Плетнёва, С. А. 1967. От кочевий к городам. Салтово-маяцкая культура. – Материалы и исследования по археологии СССР 146, 1-196.
- Плетнёва, С. А. 1959. Керамика Саркела – Белой Вежи. – Материалы и исследования по археологии СССР 75, 212-272.
- Приходнюк, О. М. 2005. Пастирське городище. Київ-Чернівці.
- Приходнюк, О. М. 2001. Степове населення України та східні слов'яни (друга половина I тис. н. е.). Київ-Чернівці.
- Приходнюк, О. М. 1998. Пеньковская культура: культурно-хронологический аспект исследования. Воронеж.
- Приходнюк, О. М. 1990. Новые данные о пеньковской культуре в Среднем Поднепровье. In: Плетнёва, С. А. / Русанова, И. П. (eds.) Раннеславянский мир. Материалы и исследования. Москва. 75-108.
- Приходнюк, О. М. 1980. Археологічні пам'ятки Середнього Подніпров'я VI – IX ст. Київ.
- Приходнюк, О. М. / Смиленко, А. Т. / Терпиловский, Р. В. 1990. Славяне и окружающий мир. In: Баран, В. Д. (ed.). Славяне Юго-Восточной Европы в предгосударственный период. Киев. 322-334.
- Приходнюк, О. М. / Хардаев, В. М. 1998. Харивский клад. – Archaeoslavica 3, 243-282.
- Путешествие Ибн Фадлана 2016. Путешествие Ибн Фадлана: Волжский путь от Багдада до Булгара. Каталог выставки. Москва.
- Рашиев, Р. 2008. Българската езическа култура VII–IX в. София.
- Рашиев, Р. 2004. Прабългарите през V-VII век. София.
- Рашиев, Р. 2000. Прабългарите през V-VII век. Велико Търново.
- Родинкова, В. Е. 2012. Новая находка византийского серебряного сосуда с клеймом в восточной Европе. – Российская археология 4, 151-158.
- Рутковская, Л. М. 1974. О стратиграфии и хронологии древнего поселения около с. Стецовки на р. Тясмине. In: Третьяков, П. Н. (ed.). Раннесредневековые восточнославянские древности. Ленинград. 22-39.
- Русаков, О. М. / Загний, Г. Ф. 1977. Отчёт по теме: «Создание опорной шкалы для датировки археологических объектов». – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund 12, # 1096.
- Семёнов, А. И. 1985. Художественный металл Романовского погребения на Дону. In: Луконин, В. Г. (ed.). Художественные памятники и проблемы культуры Востока. Ленинград. 90-100.
- Семёнов, А. И. 1991. Византийские монеты келегейского комплекса. – Археологический сборник Государственного Эрмитажа 31, 121-130.
- Смиленко, А. Т. 1975. Слов'яни та їх сусіди в Степовому Подніпров'ї (II-XIII ст.). Київ.
- Станилов, С. 1984. Селища и аули. Някои въпроси за преселването и усядането на прабългарите на Долния Дунав – VII-VIII в. In: Ангелов, Д. / Бешевлиев, В. / Гюзелев, В. / Василев, Р. / Станилов, С. (eds.). Сборник в памет на проф. Станчо Ваклинов. София. 100-105.
- Станчев, С. / Иванов, С. 1958.

- Некрополът до Нови пазар. София.
- Сухобоков, О. В. 1977. До питання про пам'ятки волинського типу. – Археологія 21, 50-66.
- Тахтаї, А. 1932. Келегейський “скарб” 1927 р. – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund ВУАК, # 116/48.
- Тахтаї, А. 1930. Ново-Санджарівський клад 1928 р. (попередне подання). – Scientific Archive of the Institute of Archaeology NASU, fund ВУАК, # 109/17a.
- Тотев, Б. / Пелевина, О. 2011. Съкровището от Врап и елитарната култура на дунавските българи. – Археологія 52, 2, 32-52.
- Тотев, Б. / Пелевина, О. 2010. „Находките“ от Веліно и Златари на аристократическите гарнітури на дунавските българи. – Археологія 51/3-4, 58-77.
- Уварова, П. С. 1902. Коллекции Кавказского музея. Археологія 5. Тифліс.
- Фабриціус, І. 1927. Літопис музею: Червоні роки 1917-1927. Херсон.
- Флєров, В. С. 2000. О технологии изготовления салтово-маяцкой лощеной керамики. – Археологія восточно-европейской лесостепи 14, 111-119.
- Флєров, В. С. 1984. Маяцкий могильник. In: Плетнёва, С. А. (ed.). Маяцкое городище: Труды советско-болгаро-венгерской экспедиции. Москва. 142-199.
- Флєров, В. С. 1981. Распространение лощеной керамики на территории салтово-маяцкой культуры. – Плиска-Преслав 2, 170-181.
- Флєров, В. С. 1976. Лощеная керамика Саркела-Белой Вежи. – Советская археологія 2, 57-66.
- Хасенова, Б. М. 2015. Курган тюркского времени могильника Ачитасты 27 в Туррае. In: Бейсенов,
- А. З. (ed.). Древний Тургай и великая степь: часть и целое. Сборник научных статей, посвященный 70-летию юбилею Виктора Николаевича Логвина. Костанай / Алматы. 212-222.
- Хлебникова, Т. А. 1984. Керамика памятников Волжской Болгарии: К вопросу об этнокультурном составе населения. Москва.
- Хрисимов, Н. 2009. Вознесенский комплекс: проблемы датировки и интерпретации. – Степи Европы в эпоху средневековья 7, 9-42.
- Христова, М. 2015. Керамика из биритуальных могильников Нижнего Дуная и вопросы ее хронологии. – Поволжская археологія 1, 91-125.
- Христова, М. 2011. Керамиката от биритуалните некрополи (VII-IX в.). Автореферат на дисертация. София.
- Щеглова, О. А. 1990. О двух группах «древностей антов» в Среднем Поднепровье. In: Терпиловский, Р. В. (ed.). Материалы и исследования по археологии Днепровского Левобережья. Курск. 162-204.
- Яворницький, Д. 2010. Справоздання Запорізької Науково-Археологічної експедиції по дослідженню території Дніпрельстану, Дніпрозаводбуду й порожистої ланки Дніпра за її роботу протягом року 1930-го. Археологічні досліді на дніпрових порогах 1927-1929 р.р. In: Коростильов, Т. (ed.). Дніпрогесівська археологічна експедиція 1927-1932 рр. (Звіти Д. І. Яворницького). (= Старожитності Південної України 23). Запоріжжя. 36-47.
- Aibabin, A. 2006. Early Khazar Archaeological Monuments in Crimea and to the North of the Black Sea. In: Zuckerman, C. (ed.). La Crimée entre Byzance et le Khaganat khazar. Paris. 31-65.
- Balint, Cs. 1989. Die Archäologie der Steppe: Steppenvölker zwischen Volga und Donau vom 6 bis zum 10 Jh. Wien / Köln.
- Curta, F. 2008. The North-Western Region of the Black Sea during the 6th and Early 7th Century AD. – Ancient West & East 7, 149-185.
- Dodd, E. C. 1992. The Location of Silver Stamping: Evidence from Newly Discovered Stamps. In: Boyd, S. A. / Mango, M. M. (eds.). Ecclesiastical Silver Plate in Sixth-Century Byzantium: Papers of the Symposium Held May 16 – 18, 1986 at the Walters Art Gallery, Baltimore and Dumbarton Oaks. Washington, D.C. 217-224.
- Dodd, E. C. 1964. Byzantine Silver Stamps, Supplement I: New Stamps from the Reigns of Justin II and Constans II. – Dumbarton Oaks Papers 18, 238-248.
- Dodd, E. C. 1961. Byzantine Silver Stamps (= Dumbarton Oaks Studies 7). Washington.
- Fiedler, U. 1992. Studien zu Gräberfeldern des 6. bis 9. Jahrhunderts an der unteren Donau. Bonn.
- Flërov, V. S. 1990. Einige Arten der polierten Keramik der Sattovo-Majaki-Kultur. In: Balint, Cs. (ed.). Die Keramik der Saltovo-Majaki Kultur und ihrer Varianten (= Varia Archaeologica Hungarica 3). Budapest. 122-136.
- Garam, E. 1992. Die münzdatierten Gräber der Awarenzeit. In: Daim, F. (ed.). Awarenforschungen I. Wien. 135-250.
- Hahn, W. 1981. Moneta Imperii Byzantini III. Wien.
- Kazanski, M. 2013. The Middle Dnieper Area in the Seventh Century: An Archaeological Survey. In: Zuckerman, C. (ed.). Constructing the Seventh Century (= Travaux et mémoires 17). Paris. 769-864.
- Kazanski, M. 1987. Note sur le peuplement de la région du Dniepr moyen pendant la seconde moitié du VII^e siècle et au VIII^e siècle. – Revue Archéologique 1, 84-90.

Krasil'nikov, K. J. 1990. Die Keramik der Saltovo-Majaki Kultur am nördlichen Mittellauf des Donec. In: Balint, Cs. (ed.). Die Keramik der Saltovo-Majaki Kultur und ihrer Varianten (= Varia Archaeologica Hungarica 3). Budapest. 193-244.

Pavón-Carrasco, F. J. / Rodríguez-González, J. / Osete, M. L. / Torta, J. M. 2011. A Matlab Tool for Archaeomagnetic Dating. – Journal of Archaeological Science 38, 2, 408-419.

Pósta, B. 1905. Archaeologische Studien auf russischem Boden 2. Budapest /

Leipzig.

Prichodnjuk, O. M. / Chardaev, V. M. 2001. Ein Edelmetallfund des 6.-7. Jhs. n. Chr. aus Kelecej, Ukraine. – Eurasia Antiqua 7, 585-612.

Rusakov, O. M. / Zagniy, G. F. 1973a. Archaeomagnetic Secular Variation Study in the Ukraine and Moldavia. – Archaeometry 15, 1, 153-157.

Rusakov, O. M. / Zagniy, G. F. 1973b. Intensity of the Geomagnetic Field in the Ukraine and Moldavia during the Past 6000 Years. – Archaeometry 15

(2), 275-285.

Smilenko, A. T. 1990. Die Keramik der Töpferwerkstätten von Balka Kancerka im Dneprgebiet. In: Balint, Cs. (ed.). Die Keramik der Saltovo-Majaki Kultur und ihrer Varianten (= Varia Archaeologica Hungarica 3). Budapest. 313-325.

Somogyi, P. 1997. Byzantinische Fundmünzen der Awarenzeit (= Monographien zur Frühgeschichte und Mittelalterarchäologie 5). Innsbruck.

Археологическо и археомагнитно датиране на ранносредновековния Канцирка тип керамика

Олексий КОМАР

(резюме)

Ранносредновековният алански керамичен производствен център в долината Канцирка на река Днепър е първото свидетелство за възобновяване на масово занаятчийско производство на стоки в северночерноморските степи в следримско време. Керамиката, създадена в Канцирка, има несъмнено алански, севернокавказки корени. Учените търсят причините за миграцията на население към Поднепровието, изследват продължителността на неговите селища. Хронологията им е основен въпрос. Скоро след откриването ѝ керамиката от типа Канцирка е датирана във втората половина на VII – VIII век по паралели от номадски комплекси с монети. След 1973 година са добавени три археомагнитни датировки „VI-VII век“ на грънчарски пещи в селището Любимивка в долината Канцирка. Те се различават от археологическите. Това води до две тълкувания на керамичния център в Канцирка. Според първото той възниква в резултат на преселване на севернокавказко население в рамките на Хазарския хаганат (след 665 година), преди формиране на Салтовската култура на Дон в средата на VIII век. Втората теза се основава на археомагнитното датиране и свързва центъра с прабългарския племенен съюз от VI-VII век с последващо пренасяне на грънчарската тради-

ция на Долния Дунав след 681 година. Съвременният анализ на археологически комплекси на номади и славяни на Днепър, съдържащи съдове от тип Канцирка, не подкрепя датиранието на появата на този грънчарски център в VI век. *Terminus post quem* за възникването му дават византийски монети от археологическия комплекс Келегей, отсечени в 644-645 година. Горната дата на съществуване на центъра в Канцирка се определя по сходство в техниката на производство на кани в долината Таранив (Мачухи) и в Салтовската култура на Дон. Археологически керамиката тип Канцирка може да се отнесе към периода 645-740 година.

Засега липсват доказателства за пренос на грънчарски традиции от Канцирка на Долния Дунав чрез прабългарите, водени от Аспарух. В три прабългарски некропола – Бдинци, Балчик и Кюлевча – са намерени съдове, напоящи по украса и форма на кани от Канцирка. Въпросните погребения датират от края на VII – средата на VIII век. Хронологически те съответстват на номадски комплекси от Поднепровието, съдържащи оригинална керамика от тип Канцирка.

През 1982 година са публикувани нови археомагнитни датировки на пещи от Канцирка. Две (# 13 и 17) са отнесени към VII век, а една (# 12) – към VIII век. Съвременна проверка на старите археомагнитни датировки дава напълно приемливи резултати, съпадащи с археологическите: пещ 13 – 634-723 година; пещ 17 – 691-770 година; пещ 12 – 704-769 година. Тези датировки ще бъдат уточнени с развитието на археомагнитния метод като анализиращи уреди и база данни.

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